

1 **Discovery of adjunctive agents for use with hormone deprivation therapy in breast cancer with**
2 **tamoxifen, letrozole, anastrozole or exemestane.**

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7 These agents are different from those that target kinases specifically expressed in the HR+ molecular
8 subtypes. Kinases activated by exposure to tamoxifen in human cells included MAP3K6 and STK40.

9 Citations

10 1. Li, L., Sun, L., Gao, F., Jiang, J., Yang, Y., Li, C., Gu, J., Wei, Z., Yang, A., Lu, R. and Ma, Y.,
11 2010. Stk40 links the pluripotency factor Oct4 to the Erk/MAPK pathway and controls extraembryonic
12 endoderm differentiation. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 107(4), pp.1402-1407.
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